
The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

Golan Hasan¹, Winky2141311²,

^{1,2}Faculty of Economics and Business University International Batam, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of Social Influence, Hedonic, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Easy to Use, and Attitude on E-WOM. A total of 238 valid data have been obtained to conduct research. The data obtained will be analyzed using the SmartPLS data analysis method to test direct and indirect relationships between variables. The results of this study show that Social Influence, Hedonic, Perceived Usefulness, and Perceived Easy to Use have a significant effect on buyer Attitude. Attitude, Hedonic, and Perceived Easy to Use have a significant effect on E-WOM. These findings provide a reference that goods sold in E-commerce or physical stores need to pay attention to Social Influence, Hedonic, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Easy to Use, and Attitude in order to create E-WOM.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Hedonic, Perceived Easy to Use, Perceived Usefulness, Social Influence

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the era is so modern that anything can be done online, such as shopping for goods on the E-commerce application. Changes in the era that are increasingly sophisticated allow humans to buy daily necessities through the E-commerce application using smartphones, laptops, and tablets. However, the use of the E-commerce application still requires the internet, with the internet everything related to human daily life will be easy and the use of the internet is also very easy for its users (Rosiana et al., 2020). This convenience can occur due to human intelligence in improving technology from time to time so that the future is increasingly sophisticated and modern.

With the changes in the era that are increasingly modern and sophisticated, it cannot be separated from the Internet. In 2020, the number of internet users was 196.7 million people or equivalent to 73.7% of the population of Indonesia. Most contributors in terms of the largest internet usage are in West Java, as many as 35.1 million people. At this time, the internet continues to develop for the better and has been widely used by various people around the world to do various things. The development of the internet that has occurred has created a modern lifestyle, such as communicating using only a smartphone or laptop, getting various information in the world, ease of shopping online. Shopping online is one of the benefits of the internet that greatly helps human life. Therefore, shopping online or online-based product marketing (E-commerce) provides convenience for producers in selling products online or E-commerce and provides convenience for consumers in buying products and searching for products online or in E-commerce applications.

E-commerce is part of a business activity that uses database technology, e-mail (electronic mail), and non-computer technology for shipping goods that have been purchased and involves payment methods for products that have been purchased. E-commerce application users in Indonesia have no age limit so that children, teenagers and adults can use the E-commerce application to shop. The existence of E-commerce creates a new strategy to increase the effectiveness of business marketing.

The ease of making purchases through E-commerce and being very efficient in shopping time makes researchers conduct research on social influence and ease of use of E-commerce applications and to fill gaps in existing literature and contribute to new literature with not much previous research. Researchers also conducted research on the hedonic and usefulness of E-commerce applications in online shopping. Based on the data above, it can be said how important it is to pay attention to things like social influence, Hedonic, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Easy to Use and Attitude in Intention to Spread E-WOM. Social influence is an important aspect of information dissemination. Social influence is also defined as the pressure felt by individuals against something (Rahim Amihisa et al., 2020). Social influence has a very big impact on attitude.

Hedonic is a feeling felt by an individual such as comfort, pleasure, and relaxation from using an item (Ekawati et al., 2021). Hedonic value is very attached to a brand that can create attraction. Not only pleasure, hedonic also refers to aesthetic value, experience and enjoyment (Lee et al., 2021).

The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

Perceived Usefulness is an indicator for future purchases because it affects interest and usefulness (Mulyani et al., 2021). This will affect the usefulness of an item purchased. The results of the usefulness of an item will affect people's purchases and interest in purchasing the item.

Perceived Easy to Use is one aspect where users of an application, goods or others feel easy to use. This also refers to ease of use in various settings (Yoon et al., 2020). Perceived ease of use plays an important role, and the perception of usefulness is defined as the extent to which individuals can believe in it (Kasilingam, 2020).

Attitude is an attitude that will be assessed positively or negatively (Choirisa et al., 2021). Attitude influences a person in acting (Chu et al., 2020). Attitude influences a person in making decisions and this will be assessed by others. Currently, internet use is very widespread in the world. Nowadays, communication is greatly assisted by the internet because it has a wide reach and is also easy to access. E-WOM is a conversation with other people to provide information about something on the internet by sharing experiences or posts about things experienced and felt by users.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Influence can change a person's behavior and thoughts from the results of their interactions with other individuals or groups (Purboyo et al., 2022). The use of social media worldwide has increased by 7% per year, this shows that social media has power in social interactions today (Cheng et al., 2021). Social influence can also change a person's attitude in terms of communication. The level of influence is divided into 2, namely acceptance and compliance. Acceptance is a condition where an individual fully accepts the influence while compliance is a condition where an individual does not accept the influence. Therefore, social influence is very influential on society in making decisions, especially in today's era, social influence can be found anywhere such as on social media, television broadcast programs, and other entertainment applications.

Hedonic is something that makes people experience experiences, fantasies, emotions and pleasure (Ekawati et al., 2021). Hedonic also greatly influences a person's desire to shop more so that they spend a lot of money but still feel pleasure (Novela et al., 2020). In the decision-making process, it will always be followed by hedonic values and their functionality (Lee et al., 2021). Hedonic can be interpreted as a form of all consumer evaluations that are based on fulfilling consumer pleasure by choosing a quality place and comfort for consumers (Hu, 2021). Social shopping is an activity carried out with a park or family so that interactions occur with them when traveling or visiting shopping places. With this, in terms of E-WOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) it can be influenced by the hedonic owned by a person so that E-WOM occurs.

Perceived Usefulness is the probability that is assessed subjectively directly by individuals who use existing applications or technologies. Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Easy to Use are two key variables related to the mechanism of technology adoption (Kim et al., 2021). Perceived Usefulness is related to how practical and useful technology is in everyday life and how individuals' attitudes towards the technology are (Prihatini & Dewi, 2022). Perceived Usefulness has an indirect effect on intention to use, because currently positive attitudes towards technology are very high (Liesa-Orús et al., 2023 and Nathania et al., 2021). Family attitudes can also influence Perceived Usefulness (Zheng & Li, 2020). By increasing the quality and service system, it will have an impact on companies that can create a sense of satisfaction for their customers while providing increased performance (Mon et al., n.d.). Perceived usefulness is a system that can help daily activities (Purwianti, 2019).

Perceived Easy to Use is a stage where individuals believe that the technology or activity being carried out is easy to do and does not require much effort to understand it (Vahdat et al., 2021 and Setiawan & Setyawati, 2020). Not only is it easy to use, but the technology or activity must be trusted by its users. Individual trust in the technology or activity being carried out is all supported by the security system owned by the technology or activity. The higher the perception of ease of use of the technology or activity, the higher the technology or activity is carried out or used. Customer experience related to the benefits and usefulness of the technology or activity, especially its ease of use, will explain the individual's intentions (Prastiawan et al., 2021).

Shopping on E-Commerce applications has become a habit in today's era. Therefore, every buyer will always involve their attitude in buying goods and their level of satisfaction (Chih et al., 2020). Attitude is an attitude defined as a person's feelings (Sandi A et al., 2022). The attitude in question is a person's attractive attitude and their intention to do something and a person's behavior or attitude can influence purchases and influence a person's intention to spread the information on the internet (E-WOM) (Conference, 2020). Not only the individual, the behavior and attitudes of people around the buyer also affect the results of the decisions and attitudes of the buyer and are defined as the extent to which a person assesses E-WOM (Abedi et al., 2020). Many things influence the attitude of buyers such as hedonic, social influence, perceived usefulness and perceived easy to use. These things greatly affect attitudes and intentions but depend on the usefulness and benefits that will be felt by the buyer (Rizkitysha & Hananto, 2022).

Consumer attitude is the most important factor. Attitude is an expression made by a person through measuring certain objects with positive or negative responses and will affect the actor's intentions (Di Stefano et al., 2023). Consumers tend to look for information about products before buying them. Social networks such as social influence are very influential in marketing. Marketing carried out by social influence can be done anywhere and nowadays many people use social media so that it involves E-WOM (Pang, 2021). Current technological advances have made WOM evolve into E-WOM where WOM expressed via the internet is called E-WOM (Gosal et al., 2020). Hedonic value is related to E-WOM because the perception of people's experiential and emotional values which

The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

are attitudes in doing so can occur through E-WOM (Spread E-WOM). Social Influence and attitudes (Attitude) involving Hedonic have a significant positive relationship with current technology which can occur Spread E-WOM (Abima et al., 2021). E-WOM has become a communication tool that is often used to find reliable information (Marninda & Kesumahati, 2023).

III. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

The measuring instrument in the test was carried out using PLS/SEM. To test the validity of the data for this study, using the outer loading method. The approach is used to evaluate how significantly certain factors contribute to the indicators of the relevant variables. To assess the validity of the questions in the questionnaire referring to the outer loading values, where the questions are considered valid if the outer loading value is > 0.6 (Hair et al., 2019).

The purpose of this test is none other than to prevent errors in measuring or analyzing data. One source of error in measuring data is method variance. To determine whether this issue occurs or not, the Single Factor Test technique is used. This test adheres to the principle of trying to include all items from all research constructs into factor analysis to determine whether the majority of the variance can be explained by one common factor. In the context of this study, it is recommended that no single factor explains more than 50% of its variance so that it is stated that there is no CMB. Based on the CMB test, it can be interpreted that the % variance value is 36.78% which is less than 50%, so that the modeling is stated to meet the criteria and there is no bias.

Based on the evaluation results, it can be concluded that all questions related to the research variables have an outer loading > 0.6 , indicating their validity, and no indicators need to be deleted. Thus, all elements of the question can be used in the next step to test its reliability. To ensure the validity of the relationship between the variables in this study, a convergent validity test known as Extractive Variance Analysis (AVE) was carried out. Convergent validity testing is considered qualified if the AVE value obtained is > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2019). Cross Loadings, this approach aims to show the relationship between each indicator and its construct. This approach is based on the requirement that the indicators accumulated in each variable must have a minimum value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). Based on the results listed in Table 6, it can be concluded that there are still many indicators that are not valid, because their values are less than 0.7.

Based on the results of the development of previous studies and the measuring instruments used, the hypothesis in this study is

H1: Social Influence has a significant positive effect on Attitude.

H2: Hedonic has a significant positive effect on Attitude.

H3: Perceived Usefulness has a significant positive effect on Attitude.

H4: Perceived Easy to Use has a significant positive effect on Attitude.

H5: Attitude has a significant positive effect on Spread E-WOM.

H6: Social Influence mediated through Attitude has a significant positive effect on Intention Spread E-WOM.

H7: Hedonic mediated through Attitude has a significant positive effect on Intention Spread E-WOM.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the results of the questionnaire obtained from 238 respondents for 1 month, all were valid, so that a total of 238 data can be used in this research.

Respondent data includes gender, age, last education, occupation, and duration of social media use in a day. In terms of gender, most respondents (59.2%) studied were male, with a total of 141 people. This was followed by 97 females with a percentage of 40.8%. Furthermore, in terms of age, most respondents were 18-23 years old, with a percentage of 67.6%, followed by 18.5% of respondents aged 24-29 years, 7.1% under 18 years old, 5.9% aged between 30-35 years, and the remaining 0.8% of respondents were over 35 years old.

Then from their last education, most respondents researched (63.9%) or 152 people had a high school/vocational high school education, followed by 23.1% of respondents with a bachelor's degree, 6.3% with a diploma, 3.8% with a junior high school education, 1.3% with a master's degree, 1.3% with an elementary school education, and 0.4% with a doctoral degree. For their jobs, the most respondents (52.1%) or 124 people were students, 29.8% were private employees, 7.6% were students, 6.3% were entrepreneurs, 2.9% were civil servants, and the remaining 1.3% were unemployed. Furthermore, based on the length of time they use social media in a day, exactly half of the respondents (50.0%) or 119 people use social media for 5 hours a day, 24.8% of respondents use social media for 1-3 hours a day, 20.8% of respondents use it for 10 hours a day, and there are 4.6% of respondents who use social media for more than 10 hours a day.

Path Coefficients, the main purpose of conducting this path coefficient test is none other than to identify the direct influence formed on its variables, without going through a mediator. In this context, the value of the relationship between variables can be indicated from the value of the t statistic and its p. A relationship is categorized as significant if $t > 1.96$, and $p < 0.05$.

The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

Table 1. Path Coefficients Test Results

	<i>T Statistics</i>	<i>P Values</i>	<i>Hipotesis</i>	<i>Result</i>
<i>Attitude -> Intention to Spread E-WOM</i>	8.924	0.000	H1	Support
<i>Hedonic -> Attitude</i>	2.959	0.003	H2	Support
<i>Perceived Easy to Use -> Attitude</i>	2.235	0.026	H3	Support
<i>Perceived Usefulness -> Attitude</i>	0.734	0.463	H4	Not Support
<i>Social Influence -> Attitude</i>	3.344	0.001	H5	Support

Source: Primary Data by Author 2024

Indirect Effects, For the assessment of the structural model involved in mediation, it is used in testing its indirect effects, in measuring the magnitude of the influence of one variable on another. The measurement is carried out through the t and p value indicators. The relationship between variables is significant if the p value <0.05, and t > 1.96 (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 2. Results of Indirect Effects Test

	<i>T Statistics</i>	<i>P Values</i>	<i>Hipotesis</i>	<i>Result</i>
<i>Hedonic -> Intention to Spread E-WOM</i>	2.600	0.010	H6	Support
<i>Perceived Easy to Use -> Intention to Spread E-WOM</i>	2.108	0.036	H7	Support

Source: Primary Data by Author 2024

Based on the research results that have been described, the results of the research discussion can be drawn that:

1. The findings of the H1 test indicate that Attitude has a significant influence on the intention to spread E-WOM. Proven by the T value of 8.924 and the p value of 0.000.
2. The findings of the H2 test indicate that Hedonic has a significant influence on Attitude. Proven by the T value of 2.959 and the p value of 0.003.
3. The findings of the H3 test indicate that Perceived easy to use has a significant influence on Attitude. Proven by the T value of 2.235 and the p value of 0.026.
4. The findings of the H4 test indicate that Perceived Usefulness does not have a significant influence on Attitude. Proven by the T value of 0.734 and the p value of 0.463.
5. The findings of the H5 test indicate that Social Influence has a significant influence on Attitude. Proven by the T value of 3.344 and the p value of 0.001.
6. The findings of the H6 test indicate that Hedonic has a significant influence on the intention to spread E-WOM. This is proven by the T-value of 2.600 and the p-value of 0.010.
7. The findings of the H7 test indicate that Perceived easy to use has a significant influence on the Intention to spread E-WOM. This is proven by the T-value of 2.108 and the p-value of 0.036.

Quality Index Test Results, the purpose of this test is none other than to evaluate the quality of a research model. In using the SMART PLS program, the index used is goodness of fit, as explained by Hair et al (2019). Goodness of fit is a comparison between a model that has been specifically described with the observed covariance matrix. The assessment of goodness of fit is classified as low if the value is more than 0.10, medium if the value is more than 0.25, and high if the value is more than 0.36. The GoF index in this study was declared high because the result was 0.492.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The results of the study stated that Perceived Usefulness towards Attitude was not supported, because conditions in the field found that individuals who use existing applications or technologies have not given a good impact on the use and utilization of E-WOM. This study is not free from limitations, such as in the distribution of questionnaires held online via google form. This is because the questionnaire tends to only be distributed to people known to the researcher. Furthermore, data collection was only carried out in a relatively short period of time, namely for 1 month, using data from 238 research samples. The variables discussed also use independent variables of social influence, hedonic, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use towards attitude (mediator variables) and intention to spread E-WOM (dependent variables).

The recommendations submitted by the researcher include:

The next researcher can express the discussion using other variables that can influence the intention to spread WOM, or with the application of different objects, in different scopes.

The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

Entrepreneurs and marketers can consider strategies to increase social influence, hedonic, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use on their online applications to maximize positive behavior and interest from customers to recommend their products/services to others.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abedi, E., Ghorbanzadeh, D., & Rahegh, A. (2020). Influence of eWOM information on consumers' behavioral intentions in mobile social networks: Evidence of Iran. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 17(1), 84–109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAMR-04-2019-0058>
- 2) Abima, B., Engotoit, B., Kituyi, G. M., Kyeyune, R., & Koyola, M. (2021). Relevant local content, social influence, digital literacy, and attitude toward the use of digital technologies by women in Uganda. *Gender, Technology and Development*, 25(1), 87–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718524.2020.1830337>
- 3) Cheng, G., Cherian, J., Sial, M. S., Mentel, G., Wan, P., Álvarez-Otero, S., & Saleem, U. (2021). The relationship between csr communication on social media, purchase intention, and e-wom in the banking sector of an emerging economy. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(4), 1025–1041. <https://doi.org/10.3390/JTAER16040058>
- 4) Chih, W. H., Hsu, L. C., & Ortiz, J. (2020). The antecedents and consequences of the perceived positive eWOM review credibility. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 120(6), 1217–1243. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-10-2019-0573>
- 5) Choirisa, S. F., Purnamaningsih, P., & Alexandra, Y. (2021). the Effect of E-Wom on Destination Image and Attitude Towards To the Visit Intention in Komodo National Park, Indonesia. *Journal of Tourism Destination and Attraction*, 9(1), 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.35814/tourism.v9i1.1876>
- 6) Chu, S. C., Chen, H. T., & Gan, C. (2020). Consumers' engagement with corporate social responsibility (CSR) communication in social media: Evidence from China and the United States. *Journal of Business Research*, 110(March 2018), 260–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.01.036>
- 7) Di Stefano, G., Ruggieri, S., Bonfanti, R. C., & Faraci, P. (2023). Entrepreneurship on Social Networking Sites: The Roles of Attitude and Perceived Usefulness. *Behavioral Sciences*, 13(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13040323>
- 8) Ekawati, N. W., Yasa, N. N. K., Kusumadewi, N. M. W., & Setini, M. (2021). The effect of hedonic value, brand personality appeal, and attitude towards behavioral intention. *Management Science Letters*, 11, 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.8.008>
- 9) Gosal, J., Andajani, E., & Rahayu, S. (2020). The Effect of e-WOM on Travel Intention, Travel Decision, City Image, and Attitude to Visit a Tourism City. *115(Insyma)*, 261–265. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200127.053>
- 10) Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). The Results of PLS-SEM Article information. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24.
- 11) Hu, Y. (2021). An improvement or a gimmick? The importance of user perceived values, previous experience, and industry context in human–robot service interaction. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 21(May), 100645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2021.100645>
- 12) Kasilingam, D. L. (2020). Understanding the attitude and intention to use smartphone chatbots for shopping. *Technology in Society*, 62, 101280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101280>
- 13) Kim, J., Merrill, K., & Collins, C. (2021). AI as a friend or assistant: The mediating role of perceived usefulness in social AI vs. functional AI. *Telematics and Informatics*, 64(February), 101694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2021.101694>
- 14) Lee, Y. K., Lee, C. K., Lee, W., & Ahmad, M. S. (2021). Do hedonic and utilitarian values increase pro-environmental behavior and support for festivals? *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 26(8), 921–934. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2021.1927122>
- 15) Liesa-Orús, M., Latorre-Coscolluela, C., Sierra-Sánchez, V., & Vázquez-Toledo, S. (2023). Links between ease of use, perceived usefulness and attitudes towards technology in older people in university: A structural equation modelling approach. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(3), 2419–2436. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11292-1>
- 16) Marninda, C., & Kesumahati, E. (2023). Peningkatan Purchase Intention Dalam Peran e-WOM dan Celebrity Endorser Pada Produk Skincare Internasional. *Ekonomi, Keuangan, Investasi Dan Syariah (EKUITAS)*, 5(2), 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.47065/ekuitas.v5i2.4465>
- 17) Mon, M. D., Aidil Basri, M., Hasan, G., Setyawan, A., Bisnis, F., & Manajemen, D. (n.d.). *Asian Journal of Management Entrepreneurship and Social Science* Anteseden and the impact of organizational culture on the civil apparatus of the state. 03(04), 1249–1271. <https://ajmesc.com/index.php/ajmesc>
- 18) Mulyani, V. G., Najib, M. F., & Guterres, A. D. (2021). The Effect of Perceived Usefulness, Trust and Visual Information toward Attitude and Purchase Intention. *Journal of Marketing Innovation (JMI)*, 1(01), 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.35313/jmi.v1i01.12>
- 19) Nathania, L., Indarini, & Anandya, D. (2021). The Effects of External Factors on Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Attitude Towards Use, and Behavioral Intention of Older Adults in Indonesia. *Proceedings of the 18th*

The Influence of Social Influence and Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Spread E-WOM Mediated by Attitude

International Symposium on Management (INSYMA 2021), 180(Insyma), 152–156.

<https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.210628.025>

- 20) Novela, S., Sihombing, Y. O., Novita, Caroline, E., & Octavia, R. (2020). The effects of hedonic and utilitarian motivation toward online purchase intention with attitude as intervening variable. *Proceedings of 2020 International Conference on Information Management and Technology, ICIMTech 2020*, August, 75–80.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIMTech50083.2020.9211197>
- 21) Pang, H. (2021). Identifying associations between mobile social media users' perceived values, attitude, satisfaction, and eWOM engagement: The moderating role of affective factors. *Telematics and Informatics*, 59(December 2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2020.101561>
- 22) Prastiawan, D. I., Aisjah, S., & Rofiaty, R. (2021). The Effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Social Influence on the Use of Mobile Banking through the Mediation of Attitude Toward Use. *Asia Pacific Management and Business Application*, 009(03), 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.apmba.2021.009.03.4>
- 23) Purboyo, P., Lamsah, L., Zulfikar, R., & Wahyuni, A. (2022). How Environment knowledge, Social Influences, and Attitude Impact The Millennial Generation's Purchase Intention in Green Products Through Attitude? *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 3(4), 1184–1194. <https://doi.org/10.46729/ijstm.v3i4.534>
- 24) Purwianti, L. (2019). Peran mediasi perceived usefulness dalam platform c2c E-commerce. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Pemasaran*.
- 25) Rahim Amihsa, A. R., Saferian, E., & Syahrir, S. (2020). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Penggunaan Mobile Payment Di Indonesia. *INTELEKTIVA: Jurnal Ekonomi, Sosial Dan Humaniora*, 2(3), 1–16.
<https://www.jurnalintelektiva.com/index.php/jurnal/article/view/306>
- 26) Rizkitysha, T. L., & Hananto, A. (2022). "Do knowledge, perceived usefulness of halal label and religiosity affect attitude and intention to buy halal-labeled detergent?" *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(3), 649–670. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-03-2020-0070>
- 27) Rosiana, L., Hubeis, M., & Cahyadi, E. R. (2020). Factors Affecting User Behavior of Technology Application of Management Information System. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 6(3), 239–248.
<https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.6.3.239>
- 28) Sandi A, A. S., Soedijono, B., & Nasiri, A. (2022). Use of Tam for Evaluation of Internship Information System. *Jurnal TAM (Technology Acceptance Model)*, 13(1), 44. <https://doi.org/10.56327/jurnaltam.v13i1.1216>
- 29) Setiawan, M., & Setyawati, C. Y. (2020). The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use on the Intention to Use Mobile Payment. *Journal of Accounting and Strategic Finance*, 3(1), 18–32. <https://doi.org/10.33005/jasf.v3i1.67>
- 30) Vahdat, A., Alizadeh, A., Quach, S., & Hamelin, N. (2021). Would you like to shop via mobile app technology? The technology acceptance model, social factors and purchase intention. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 29(2), 187–197.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2020.01.002>
- 31) Yoon, J., Vonortas, N. S., & Han, S. W. (2020). Do-It-Yourself laboratories and attitude toward use: The effects of self-efficacy and the perception of security and privacy. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 159(December 2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120192>
- 32) Zheng, J., & Li, S. (2020). What drives students' intention to use tablet computers: An extended technology acceptance model. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 102(May), 101612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101612>